

A CRITICAL STUDY ON THE EFFICACY OF KADALI PRATIKSHĀRĀNĪYA KṢHĀRA IN ARŚA (HEMORRHOIDS)- A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Arsha is fleshy projection that pains like an enemy and creates obstruction in *Guda Marga* which can be compared with haemorrhoids and one among the *Astamahagada*. *Arsha* presents with clinical features as bleeding per rectum, prolapse, feeling of mass, pain, anaemia. Peak age is 4th to 6th decade while majority of patients report regarding onset of disease in 5th decade of life and increased prevalence in women compared with men. The prime etiopathogenic factor of *Arshas* is *Mandagni*, which in turn leads to constipation, prolonged contact of accumulated *Mala* or excretory material to *Gudavali* causes development of *Arshas*. As per the available treatment modalities of *Arsha*, the *Kshara karma* modality is the best one, taking into the consideration its convenience, easy adoptability, cost effectiveness and curative results. Under this para surgical procedure, various forms of external *Kshara* application are used in treating the *Arsha*. The *Kshar*

application is described in *Sushruta samhita* in *Chikitsa sthana*. It is indicated for the treatment of *Arsha* as local application.^[1] Hence it selected for the present study to access the effectiveness in management of 2nd degree *Arsha*.

KEYWORDS: *Abhyantara Arsha, Kshara Karma, Kadali Pratisaraneeya Kshara*, Internal haemorrhoid.

INTRODUCTUION

Acharya Charaka as well as *Madhava* mentioned that the *Dushyas* of *Arsha* are *Twak, Mamsa* and *Medas*.^[2] According to Ayurveda the disease comes under the heading of *Maharogas*.^[3]

Arsha occurs in *Gudabhaga*, which is undoubtedly a *Marma*, and it is well known for its chronicity and difficult to treat. If neglected or not cured properly, it may turn into complications such as hemorrhage, thrombosis, portal pyaemia, fibrosis, strangulation, suppuration.

Acharya Sushruta has mentioned four lines of management such as: *Bhaisaja, Kshara, Agni, Shastra*.^[4] According to *Acharya Vagbhatta*, *Arsha* is a muscular projection (*Mamsakila*) which troubles the patient like an enemy^[5] and *Acharya Madhava* also followed it.^[6] *Arshas* are dealt rationally under the concept of Hemorrhoids. Hemorrhoid is a common disorder, affecting 4% of the world population which is very specific to human race due to its erect posture. Classification of a hemorrhoid corresponds to its position relative to the dentate line. Internal hemorrhoids lie above the dentate line and are derived from endoderm whereas external hemorrhoid lies below the dentate line and derived from ectoderm.^[7] Internal hemorrhoids are classified by the degree of prolapse of the anal canal. External may be classified as acute (hemorrhoidal thrombosis) or chronic (anal skin tags). In modern surgery for treatment of hemorrhoids sclerotherapy, infrared, photocoagulation, rubber band ligation laser therapy, Lord's dilatation, hemorrhoidectomy, and stapled hemorrhoidectomy are in practice but these are costly and chance of recurrence is more.

Pratiksharaniya kshara in Arsha roga: The ancient writing of Indian medical practitioners like *Sushruta, Charaka* and *Vagbhatta* provide an elaborate description of *Arsha Roga* and various modalities of treatment along with brief description of *Pratiksharaniya kshara* therapy.

Acharya Sushruta (800 BC) has described four folded line of treatment as *Bhaishaja chikitsa, Kshara karma, Agni karma* and *Shastra Karma* in management of anorectal disorders.^[8]

Among all these therapies *Kshara karma* has become very useful and recently modified method of treatment for selected anorectal diseases. *Kadali Pratishhāraṇīya Kṣhāra* A safe, minimally invasive, cost-effective approach for hemorrhoids, with *Chedana*, *bhedana*, *Lekhana*, *Sthabana*, *Shodana*, *Ropana* properties.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To evaluate the efficacy of *Ayurvedic* treatment in the conservative management of *Arsha* (internal hemorrhoids).

To demonstrate the symptomatic relief and recurrence prevention through classical *Ayurvedic* formulations and therapies.

To present a holistic, non-invasive management protocol for early-stage hemorrhoids.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Type of Study: Single case observational study

Case report

A 48 year old man presented with the complaints of bleeding during defecation, pain, heaviness in the rectal region, constipation for 3 months.

History: No history of surgery or chronic illnesses. Sedentary lifestyle, irregular food habits, frequent spicy and fast food intake.

Clinical findings

Inspection

No external piles visible at rest.

Anal verge appeared normal, with mild erythema.

No prolapse or thrombosed mass noted externally.

Digital Rectal Examination (DRE)

Anal tone: Normal

Tenderness: Mild tenderness at 7 o'clock position on digital examination

No palpable external mass

No signs of fissure or fistula

Mucosa felt slightly thickened internally

Proctoscopic/Anoscopic Examination

Grade II internal hemorrhoids seen at 3, 7, and 11 o'clock positions (typical sites).

Hemorrhoidal cushions appeared congested and enlarged.

On straining, the piles protruded into the lumen but spontaneously reduced.

Mild fresh bleeding observed during examination.

Mucosa over the piles was shiny, erythematous, and congested.

Mild burning sensation after defecation is present

No evidence of secondary infection, ulceration, or thrombosis.

Diagnosis Ayurvedic

Diagnosis: *Kaphaja Arsha*

Modern Correlation: Internal bleeding hemorrhoids (Grade II).

Treatment Plan

Pratisaraneeya Kshara Karma procedure

Purva Karma

- Consent was taken.
- Part preparation was done
- Proctoclysis enema was given
- Xylocaine sensitivity test

Pradhana Karma

Patient was made to lie down in lithotomy position. Anus and surrounding area was cleaned with antiseptic lotion. Draping was done. Local anaesthesia with 2% xylocaine was administered manual anal dilatation was done sufficient enough to admit four fingers. Lubricated normal proctoscope was introduced and position of pile mass was noted and proctoscope was removed. Then slit proctoscope was introduced and skin around pile mass was pulled laterally with Allis tissue holding forceps to get a better view of haemorrhoids.

The healthy anal mucosa was covered with wet cotton balls to prevent spilling of Kshara on it. Then the pile mass was gently scraped with the rough surface of spatula. Then *Kadali Pratisaraneeya Kshara* was applied over pile mass and the opening of proctoscope is closed for Shatamatrakala (2 minutes) with the palm. Then the pile mass was cleaned with lemon juice. After saw the pinkish pile mass was turned to blackish (*Pakva Jambu Phala Varna*), if not, *Kshara* was applied once again till the pile mass turned to blackish colour. Once again it was washed with lemon juice and sterile water wash was given. This procedure was repeated on all the haemorrhoids. Thereafter the anal canal was packed with gauze piece soaked in

Jatyadi Taila to prevent burning sensation and local oedema. Dry dressing was done and the patient was shifted to ward.

Paschat karma

- Patient was kept nil by mouth for 6 hours after the procedure.
- Packing was removed after 6 hours and 15ml of *Jatyadi Taila* was administered per rectal.
- From next day onwards patient was advised to take hot water sitz bath after passing motion for 10-15 min twice a day.
- Avipattikara churna 5gms given at night with lukewarm water as a laxative.
- Diet restriction was advised to the patient.

Shamana Chikitsa (Palliative Treatment)

- Triphala Guggulu – 500 mg twice daily after food – for bowel regulation and dosha pacification.
- Abhayarishta – 15 ml twice daily after meals – for constipation and Vata anulomana.
- Arshoghni Vati – 250 mg twice daily – for Arsha-specific relief.
- Avipattikara Churna – 5 gm at bedtime with warm water – for mild laxative effect.

Dietary and Lifestyle Advice

- Avoid spicy, oily, and constipating foods.
- Include fiber-rich diet, warm water intake.
- Encourage light exercises and regular bowel habits.
- Avoid prolonged sitting.

Follow-Up and Outcomes

Follow-Up (Weeks)	Symptoms	Remarks
1st Week	Reduced bleeding and straining	<i>Kadali pratikshara kshara</i> effective
2nd Week	No bleeding, mild pain	Continued internal medicines
4th Week	Complete relief from bleeding and pain	Lifestyle changes helped prevent relapse
6th Week	No recurrence; normal bowel movements	Medicines gradually tapered

Statistical Analysis

Symptom Severity Scores Before and After *Ayurvedic* Treatment (Likert Scale 0–4).

Symptom	Before Treatment(Score / 4)	After Treatment(Score / 4)	Score Reduction	% Improvement
Bleeding per rectum	3 – Severe	0 – None	3	100%
Pain during defecation	2 – Moderate	0 – None	2	100%
Constipation	3 – Severe	1 – Mild	2	66.7%
Rectal heaviness/discomfort	2 – Moderate	0 – None	2	100%
Frequency of bowel movements	1 – Mild irregularity	0 – Normal	1	100%
Total Symptom Score	11 / 20	1 / 20	10	90.9%

DISCUSSION

Arsha symptoms like as Bleeding per anal, *gudadaha*, *gudasrava*, *gudakandu* were successfully treated with *Ksharapatana* (local application of *Pratisaraniya Kshara* to *Arsha*). *Kshara* possesses qualities of *Chhedana*, *Bhedhana*, and *Lekhana*, and as a result, it produces a shrinking impact on pile masses. *Gudadaha* also subsided. *Daha* is caused by the vitiation of *Pitta* and *Rakta doshas*, both of which have *Amla* (acidic) properties that are mitigated by *Kshara's Lavana Anurasa*.

According to the *Acharya Sushruta*, 4 modes of haemostatic procedure are like *Sandhana*, *Skandana*, *Pachana* and *Dahana* *Kshara* is chemically caustic in nature. It has got the ability to cauterize the unhealthy tissue and it is used in the *Dahan karma*. *Kshara* contain some drugs which are of *Kashaya Rasa*.^[9] Their action is *Sandhankarama*. *Bhasma* like *Shukti* was added to the *Kshara* during the preparation of *Kshara*, its action is to perform *Pachana karma*. Thus *Kshara* may be said to have its action through all the mode of haemostatic procedure. Local application of *Kshara* was done on the base and on the haemorrhoidal mass which was present above the dentate line, during the application of *Kadali kshara* the color of haemorrhoid changes from reddish blue to *Pakvajambuvarna*. *Kshara* causes *Ksarana* (destruction), i.e. chemical cauterization. It also causes *Kshanana* (inflammation) on the base of haemorrhoidal mass. The inflammatory reaction follows proliferation of fibroblast, obliteration of haemorrhoidal plexus and prevents bleeding and fibrosis and finally the fixation of anal cushion to underlying structure which further prevent protrusion and bleeding.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the pile masses shrank out with *Kadali Pratiksharana kshara*, but did not completely disappear. As a result, *Kadaki Pratiksharanakshara* was a successful therapy for treating first and second degree haemorrhoids. The significant element was that there were no side effects or harmful consequences demonstrated following the treatment. *Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara* can relieve post-operative pain, can help in reduction of post-operative size of pile mass, help in reduction of post-operative bleeding per rectum and effectively changes the colour of pile mass after its application.

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